

D4.4: Preliminary Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

The RM ROADMAP Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation (DCE) Report summarizes the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Activities of the RM ROADMAP Consortium in the first year of the project. In particular, the report presents the launch of the Research Management Helix on the CrowdHelix Open Innovation Platform as part of the RM Roadmap Knowledge and Community Platform; the establishment of the RM Roadmap Ambassador Network; as well as broader dissemination via presentations at different fora, including conferences, webinars and media outreach.

WP4, CrowdHelix, Community, Communication and Dissemination

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

Project full
title

**“Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen
the European Research Area”**

Project acronym
RM Roadmap

Grant Agreement no.

101058475

D4.4: Preliminary Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Report

RM Roadmap_ CHX_WP4_D4.4_Preliminary Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

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List of Abbreviations, Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Definition
ASTP	Association of European Science & Technology Transfer Professionals
CHX	Crowdhelix
D	Deliverable
DARMA	Danish Association of Research Managers and Administrators
DCE	Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation
EARMA	European Association of Research Managers and Administrators
EUA	European University Association
KCP	Knowledge and Community Platform
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KOWI	European Liaison Office of the German Research Organisations
NARMA	Norwegian Network for Administration and Research Management
NGOs	Non-governmental Organisations
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RM	Research Management
RPO	Research Performing Organisations
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The Preliminary Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Report Deliverable D4.4 provides a report of the activities of the RM ROADMAP project in the first 12 months of the project (September 2022 to August 2023) regarding the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities. It serves as a progress report on Work Package (WP) 4 (Community, Communication and Dissemination). It is the second Deliverable of WP4 on Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation and it presents the activities and impact of actions that have been undertaken by the RM ROADMAP consortium partners aiming to reach as many relevant actors as possible to inform them on the objectives and activities of the project.

The community activities, communication channels, communication activities and interactions are described in D4.4 and evaluated in comparison to the goals set in the first deliverable of WP4 D4.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan, delivered in month M6 (February 2023) of the project's lifetime. In summary, RM ROADMAP has met or exceeded all goals and success criteria defined in the Grant Agreement (GA). The RM ROADMAP Project is funded by the European Commission under GA N. 101058475.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Overview

RM-ROADMAP supports research management (RM) capacity in Europe. Over 36 months, the project charts a course for the future of EU research management (RM) and creates an inclusive community to support its delivery.

The overarching goal of RM Roadmap is to identify and adapt the research management capital base of the EU, including the widening countries, and emerging needs of its current and future research management workforce to improve the EU's competitiveness and sustain its economic performance.

Such a broad outreach can be made feasible through leveraging the volunteering power of the research management community in combination with a common IT environment, engaging with networks (of networks) and establishing a new Ambassador Network. The IT environment is the Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP). Currently, most of the networking and best practice exchange in Europe is taking place through volunteering. In most cases, this happens with the support of the employers of those research managers.

The KCP of RM Roadmap is constituted of two different systems. One for the cocreation (EARMA cocreation platform) and another for dissemination and impact acceleration (CrowdHelix RM Helix).

- The EARMA cocreation platform is an upgrade of the existing EARMA community platform.
- The RM Helix is existing and proven technology.

This co-creation process gathers together the existing communities and expands upon them to reach two main objectives:

- To create and inform a bottom-up consensus on the future of RM in a roadmap
- To inform the community about existing training, networking, funding, and career mobility opportunities

Eight partners are working together on this exciting project: European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (Belgium); HETFA Research Institute (Hungary); Nova University Lisbon (Portugal); Association of European Science & Technology Transfer Professionals (Netherlands); CrowdHelix Limited (Ireland), The Cyprus Institute (Cyprus) and associated partners Janssen Pharmaceuticals (J&J) and Una Europa (Belgium).

The success of this project depends on the involvement of the research management community across Europe and beyond. Research support professionals of all levels are invited to participate in RM ROADMAP and are encouraged to join, share their views and work together to shape the future of the research management profession in Europe. Figure 1 is from the presentation of the RM ROADMAP at the second BESTPRAC Thematic Group Meeting in Limassol Cyprus – where the project was presented to the BESTPRAC network. BESTPRAC serves as a platform for exchanging experiences, sharing and developing best practices, encouraging knowledge sharing, knowledge transfer and increasing efficiency for research administrative, financial and legal staff at universities and research-driven institutions.

Figure 1. Presentation of RM ROADMAP at the BESTPRAC Thematic Group Meeting in Limassol in March 2023

1.2. Deliverable purpose

The document includes all the community, dissemination and communication activities that have been undertaken during the first twelve months of the project, as well as some still planned. DCE is an integral part of the RM ROADMAP's development processes, and while it is managed and administered from WP4 (Community, Communication, Dissemination), DCE activities may arise in all tasks across all WPs.

The deliverable is public and therefore is mainly addressed to the RM ROADMAP Consortium partners, the European Commission (funding authority), as well as other audiences who are interested in learning more about and engaging with the project.

D4.4 "Preliminary Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report" is an output of WP4 and is directly linked with Deliverable D4.1 "Dissemination Communication and Exploitation Plan" that serves as a guiding document for DCE.

1.3. DCE Definitions and Objectives

RM ROADMAP adopts Horizon Europe guidelines to provide targeted information to multiple audiences in a strategic, coherent, and effective manner. The project's DCE activities, translate into different project objectives as set out below:

Communication: *Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange².*

Dissemination: *the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications via any medium.*

² [Dissemination & Exploitation Communication Measure – EC Info, Funding & Tenders](#)

Exploitation: *the use of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating, and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities³.*

The underpinning RM ROADMAP Communication, dissemination and exploitation objectives as presented in D4.1 are listed below:

- Raise awareness of the project and its progress with key audiences
- Develop a project identity, website and social media presence
- Develop standard materials for the consortium partners to use in communications activities
- Identify opportunities to multiply the effectiveness of communications, such as project clusters and networks
- Analyse communications to identify stakeholder categories and groupings for targeted dissemination and exploitation
- Disseminate results among the RM community to be used, adopted and/or implemented directly, and to initiate and facilitate further work
- Disseminate results to relevant public agencies responsible for funding research, to support effective integration of future RM activities into research programmes
- Identify and further define key exploitable results, and map pathways to impact
- Engage with key stakeholders on the impact pathway as early as possible
- Develop and implement sustainability measures to ensure long-term exploitation of the project outcomes

An Open, Virtual Community for Research Managers and Stakeholders, working together to define our future

Figure 2. RM ROADMAP Overview

1.4. Project Audience

The RM-ROADMAP partners have initiated a process to develop a strategic approach to each category/audience, and to list key stakeholders within each category presented in D4.1.

This process will continue throughout the project, and categories may be further subdivided and refined, for

³ [EC IP Helpdesk Glossary](#)

example by geographical area of operation, or specific interest within the RM domain.

The main project audience categories were identified in the first 12 Months of RM Roadmap are listed below:

- Academic Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) – RM professionals
- Academic RTOs – Academics
- Research Manager Professional Societies
- Public Agencies
- Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and nonprofit organisations
- Policy makers
- Commercial RTOs
- Commercial Industry
- Civil Society
- Citizen organisations
- Projects and/or associations
- Exploitation partners

More information with regards to the relevance with regards to RM ROADMAP, specific messaging and communication channels and content are presented in D4.1.

A new virtual cluster community called the Research Management Helix on the Crowdhelix platform is the focal point for engaging the stakeholders at the backbone of the dissemination and exploitation strategies – for both during and after the project. More information on the Research Management Helix can be found in Section 2.9.

Figure 3. Bringing together the Research Management Community

1.5. Evolution of DCE over the project term

As presented in D4.1 activity will develop throughout the project, and beyond, as shown in Figure 4.

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Figure 4. Evolution of Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation through the RM ROADMAP project

During the first 12 months of the project, RM ROADMAP finalised the main elements of the project's visual identity and launched main communications platforms:

- the project website,
- social media channels,
- the Ambassador Network, and,
- the RM Helix.

The co-creation on the Knowledge and Community Platform will be launched in September 2023⁴ with the first co-creation topic on "UNDERSTAND THE LANDSCAPE: NATIONAL NETWORKS AND ASSOCIATIONS" starting in October 2023. Full RM Roadmap timeline is available [here](#).

Different communications materials were developed, and the project's communications and dissemination activities were initiated, as well as clustering with CARDEA, RM-ROADMAP's 'sister' project funded on the same call [HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-20], "CARDEA".

Both consortia share a strong willingness to collaborate for the good of the RM community, where synergies exist, and have already engaged early in the projects to develop a cooperation. A formal Memorandum of Understanding is currently being prepared, its signature expected for autumn 2023.

⁴ RM Roadmap Knowledge and Community Platform: How to engage on the new EARMA online co-creation space <https://earma.org/conferences/rm-roadmap-knowledge-and-community-platform/>

2. Dissemination and Communication Channels and Activities

2.1. Dissemination and Communication Overview

The dissemination and communication channels and activities up to month 12 (September 2022 to August 2023) were created based on the RM ROADMAP DCE plan i.e. D4.1, with the aim to raise awareness for the project, engage the defined stakeholders and promote the project's goals and outcomes. There was a regular flow of information about the project through the website and social media, open dialogue with defined stakeholder groups, as well as promotion of the project mostly within Europe but also internationally.

2.2. Identity and Support Materials

The brand identity informed the design of the project logo, document template and PowerPoint slide deck. The slide deck has been provided to all project partners and is available in the project's EMDESK space, so that it can be used without further additional permission. The slide deck will be maintained and updated as the RM ROADMAP project progresses.

The project identity has been developed, including a logo and document templates.

Figure 5. RM ROADMAP logos and headers

To ensure a cohesive visual identity, a set of branding guidelines has been developed as a part of D4.1. These guidelines ensure that the logo is used consistently, creating a strong and cohesive visual identity. The brand guidelines provide guidance on colours to be used in all print and online materials (such as templates and flyers).

Navy - #2a2572

Purple - #8e84b5

Light grey - #e0e2e7

White - #ffffff

Figure 6. RM ROADMAP color palette

2.3. Project Website

A dedicated website has been created and developed for the project as one of its main dissemination points.

The website has been designed to act as a “living platform” and to evolve as the project reaches its various milestones, intending to engage with key players, context setters, and advocates. As the project matures, the website will serve to meet the evolving content needs of those audiences by having key messages updated and renewed. Care has been taken to ensure that any content published on the website can be directly leveraged by the project’s social media channels.

This creates a direct link between the website and its main distribution channels and provides the project’s social media accounts with the means to engage with the audiences outlined in D4.1.

Figure 7. RM-ROADMAP Webpage (screen capture June 2023)

A project website (<https://www.rmroadmap.eu/>) went live on October 28th, 2022. With respect to the formal project plan, this represents achieving Milestone 1 with two months ahead of schedule. An additional page promoting the Ambassador Network programme was added in December 2022 and a page on News and Events in April 2023 (Figure 3). Further to this page, there are links to the RM ROADMAP Timeline updated to inform the Ambassadors and interested parties of the steps of RM ROADMAP, as well as a Meet the Team page where key personnel from the partners are presented.

Corresponding material was created to promote the Research Management Helix launch and registration to the RM Helix – that will be presented in Section 2.9 Research Management Helix Launch.

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Figure 8. RM-ROADMAP Webpage statistics (October 28, 2022 - January 9 2023)

The website statistics in the first 2.5 months of the project show the anticipation for RM ROADMAP by the RM community with a total of 747 visits.

The website statistics for M3 – M10 (January 2023 – June 2023) were even more impressive, with 16000 unique visits with an average time of just under 3 minutes. This was the result of concrete and persistent efforts of the Consortium to engage with the stakeholders. The peak number of visits occurs in February 2023 and May 2023. The peaks coincide with a) the launch of the Call for RM Roadmap Ambassadors February 2023 and b) the EARMA Annual Conference including the launch of the Research Management Helix (April 2023) and the first RM Roadmap Ambassador Network meeting (May 2023).

Open call for RM ROADMAP Ambassadors to co-create the future of research management in Europe

by gordoskatalin | Feb 9, 2023 | Division for International Cooperation, News, RM ROADMAP

The project **RM ROADMAP** aims to support the strengthening of an inclusive research management community in Europe. The project will connect existing European networks on a smart community platform (Knowledge and Community Platform), enabling an unprecedented co-creation process in research management. **HETFA** is involved as a project partner leading the *Intelligence* work package, and the consortium is led by **EARMA**.

The [open call](#) for **RM ROADMAP Ambassadors** is available on the project website. Selected Ambassadors across Europe will design the future of research management in Europe. RM ROADMAP Ambassadors will be national or regional community builders and online moderators. Up to 80 Ambassadors are anticipated to be recruited, the deadline to submit the applications is the **24th of February, 2023**.

More information and the application form are available on the project [website](#).

Figure 9. RM-ROADMAP Ambassadors Network Call Launch on HETFA Research Institute's website, linking to the RM ROADMAP website.

Figure 9 below shows the RM ROADMAP's website unique monthly visits for a 9-month period in the first 12

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months of the project. Figure 10 presents the most popular pages on the site whilst Figure 11 the website traffic source locations.

Figure 10. RM ROADMAP Webpage monthly visits (October 28,2022 – June 26, 2023 – period of 9 months)

Figure 11. RM ROADMAP Webpage most popular pages (October 28,2022 – June 26, 2023 – period of 9 months)

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Location	Visits
▶ Portugal	1,402 (8.06%)
▶ Spain	1,328 (7.63%)
▶ France	1,138 (6.54%)
▶ Netherlands	1,115 (6.41%)
▶ Belgium	1,077 (6.19%)
▶ Italy	1,003 (5.77%)
▶ Hungary	896 (5.15%)
▶ Ireland	851 (4.89%)
▶ United Kingdom	648 (3.72%)
▶ Norway	631 (3.63%)

Figure 12. Top 10 Traffic Source Locations RM ROADMAP Webpage (October 28,2022 – June 26, 2023 – period of 9 months)

Your Page Averages		
Time on Page	Bounce Rate	Exit Rate
167s	91.5%	85.54%

Figure 13. RM ROADMAP Webpage average time on page (October 28,2022 – June 26, 2023 – period of 9 months). Ideal target should be over 2 minutes.

Further information on the RM ROADMAP website analytics are included in Annex A3.

2.4 Social Media

Social media play an important role in making our stakeholders aware of the RM ROADMAP project and highlighting the project’s progress. The project plan proposed three social media channels would be established: Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook. Experience based from the consortium partners involvement with other Horizon actions, the consortium agreed that Facebook was no longer a worthwhile platform for RM-ROADMAP. As an alternative, a project home on ResearchGate was set up.

The @rmroadmap handle is secured on all three platforms during the initiation phase:

- twitter.com/RMROADMAP (Operated by Crowdhelix)
- www.linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap/ (Operated by Crowdhelix)
- www.researchgate.net/project/RM-ROADMAP (Operated by HETFA)

The account on the ResearchGate platform was closed due to comparative lack of engagement. A social media grid can be seen below which displays the rationale for the platforms that RM ROADMAP will be active on throughout the project.

Table 1. RM ROADMAP Social Media Grid

Media	Reasons
Twitter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active base of relevant stakeholders (i.e., other projects, research managers) • Effective for ‘live tweeting’ of events (i.e., plenary meetings, conferences) • Provides strong interaction and engagement with stakeholders thanks to retweets, tags, likes
LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wide base of professional stakeholders, also in the RM professions • Allows different type of engagement (i.e., more focused on dissemination than communication)

During the first year of RM ROADMAP, these channels have been used to engage with relevant accounts, and resharing information with the primary intent of building a following. In later phases, the channels will be used for dissemination and as a facilitator for stakeholder/community engagement. We plan to profile each

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Ambassador/country involved in RM Roadmap on social media on a rotating monthly basis to inform and promote their involvement in the project and activities to date.

2.4.1 Twitter

Figure 14. RM ROADMAP Twitter account (June 2023)

@RM ROADMAP is mostly used to raise awareness about the project’s progress, interact with key stakeholders, and build relationships with other Horizon Europe projects as well as to disseminate the project’s news and current results. The account has 259 followers, and 115 tweets were posted up until M12. In the table below you can see the impressions gained and the engagement rate of the project’s tweets since the beginning of the project, according to the Twitter analytics.

2.4.2 LinkedIn

The RM ROADMAP LinkedIn account has 546 followers so far, coming from multiple professional fields and various European locations. Most of the followers come from Research, and Project and Programme Management.

Figure 7: RM ROADMAP LinkedIn account (June 2023)

The Visitor Metrics on LinkedIn evaluate traffic metrics for unique visitors and page views over time. Mobile metrics include LinkedIn native apps and mobile web browsers. Unique visitors are calculated daily and are not de-duplicated over multiple days.

Figure 15. RM ROADMAP LinkedIn account visitor metrics (June 2023)

Job function

Figure 16. RM ROADMAP LinkedIn account visitor metrics per job function (June 2023)

Further information on the RM ROADMAP social media analytics are included in Annex A4.

2.5 Press and traditional media

An initial press release at before project kick-off (July 2022) was featured in Research Professional and posted to the coordinator and several partner websites.

Further media engagement has followed with project activity and the more recent press release following the launch of the Research Management Helix (April 2023) and then the RM ROADMAP Ambassadors Meeting (May 2023).

15/07/2022, 08:29

Research Professional - Research management roadmap project 'ready to launch'

15/07/2022, 08:29

Research Professional - Research management roadmap project 'ready to launch'

- 14 Jul 22, 12:30
- By Craig Nicholson
- Related Links
 - [Earma announcement](#)

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Research management roadmap project 'ready to launch'

Earma-led initiative has EU backing of €1.5 million

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A project to set out the future direction of European research management is ready to launch, the organisations leading it have announced.

The RM-Roadmap [has won €1.5 million from the EU](#) for work that "aims to define" the future of the research management profession.

Led by the European Association of Research Managers and Administrators, the project will draft a vision and strategy for research management, establish a stakeholder community and aim to build synergies between resources.

"The community remains fragmented, and recognition varies across Europe," said Earma managing director Nik Claesen. "I believe now is the right time to connect our existing European networks and create the roadmap for the future of research management in Europe."

"Later in the year we begin recruiting volunteers to co-create this roadmap by forming an ambassador network, and also build an intelligent platform to support our community on this exciting journey."

Mission support

Michael Browne, representing Crowdhelix, a research networking organisation participating in the project, said the initiative would include work on how research managers can support the EU research and innovation-based 'missions' on cancer, climate change, oceans, soil and cities.

"Research managers are a vital part of delivering research impact, strategic planning and bridging between leadership groups in complex university and research organisations," he said.

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<https://www.researchprofessional.com/01/news/europe/universities/2022/7/Research-management-roadmap-project-ready-to-launch.html>

2/3 <https://www.researchprofessional.com/01/news/europe/universities/2022/7/Research-management-roadmap-project-ready-to-launch.html>

3/3

Figure 17. RM-ROADMAP Pre-Kick Off Press Release featured in Research Professional (14 July 2022)

Research Management Helix

24 May 2023

The RM ROADMAP project (Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area) will create a roadmap for the future of research management (RM) in Europe and a community to support the delivery of that roadmap.

Coordinated by EARMA, RM-ROADMAP will connect existing European networks on a smart community platform which will enable an unprecedented co-creation process of RM in the world.

As part of the RM ROADMAP project a research management helix will be created. Helix is an international Open Innovation community of RM practitioners, specialists, and other stakeholders, as well as relevant policy makers and citizen interest groups. In addition to facilitating opportunities that can further progress the RM domain of practice, the Helix will support RM-Roadmap by accelerating community development and translation of project results into cross-sectoral impact across the European Research Area and beyond.

Learn more on the [dedicated website](#) and [download the Research Management Helix flyer](#).

[▲ TO TOP](#)

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Figure 18. RM-ROADMAP RM Helix Launch in European University Association (24 May 2023)

Figure 19. RM-ROADMAP 120 RM AMBASSADORS Event Press Release on European's Office Cyprus Website

A list of communications such as press releases and other articles are listed in the Table below.

Table 2. List of Communication Activities related to RM ROADMAP

#	Communication Activity Name	Description	Target Audience	Communication Channel
1	2022 RM Roadmap on EARMA website	14 July 2022, RM Roadmap is featured on the EARMA website: https://earma.org/roadmap/	Civil society	Website
2	2022 RM-ROADMAP Awarded, press release EARMA	14 July 2022, https://earma.org/news/press-release-mapping-future-research-management/ . Multiple partner shared; Reported on Research Professional News; https://shorturl.ac/7bgof	Civil society	Media article
3	2022 Campaign on ASTP Twitter, LinkedIn	26 July 2022, Announcement through ASTP's social channels about the RM Roadmap project.	Civil society	Social media
4	2022 Campaign on CHX Twitter, LinkedIn	2 August 2022, Announcement through Crowdhelix and RM Roadmap social channels (twitter, LinkedIn) about the RM Roadmap project.	Civil society	Social media
5	2022 RM Roadmap Project Launch	6 September 2022, Article 'Did you miss the launch of the RM Roadmap project in Belgrade?' RM-ROADMAP Project Launch	Civil society	Media article
6	2022 New Horizon Europe project launched, HETFA	20 September 2022, Online Article, https://hetfa.hu/2022/09/20/uj-horizont-europa-projekt-a-hetfanal/	Civil society	Website
7	2022 Policy brief on ERA Action 17 (I)	24 October 2022, Action 17 and its potential for the RMA community, article on how EARMA's projects and future endeavors fit into a wider pan-European strategy, https://earma.org/news/action-17/	Research communities	Media article
8	2022 RM ROADMAP on HETFA website	4 November 2022, RM Roadmap is featured on the HETFA website: https://hetfa.hu/npi/rmroadmap/ https://hetfa.eu/about-us/main-activities/division-for-international-cooperation/rm-roadmap/	Civil society	Website
9	2023 Policy brief about Action 17 (II)	26 January 2023, Why your Member State needs to support Action 17, follow-up to previous 2022 article informing about the potential of Action 17 for the research management, https://shorturl.ac/7bg	Civil society	Media article
10	2023 Open Call for RM ROADMAP Ambassadors	9 February 2023, Call for RM Roadmap ambassadors opened, https://shorturl.ac/7bgof	Research communities	Social media

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11	2023 RM Roadmap at EARMA Annual Conference	26 April 2023, Articles featured at Research Professional News: 'Game-changer' plan for research management roadmap, https://shorturl.ac/7bgoq 'Earma 2023: What's in a name?' https://shorturl.ac/7bgoq	Civil society	Media article
12	2023 Research Management Helix	24 May 2023, Article features on European University Association News https://eua.eu/partners-news/1066-research-management-helix.html	Research communities	Media Article
13	2023 RM ROADMAP Ambassadors Meeting Press Release	14 June 2023, Press release featured on Research Management related website - https://eoc.org.cy/rm-roadmap-appoints-120-expert-research-managers-as-national-ambassadors/	Research communities	Media article
14	2023 Information on RM ROADMAP and Action 17, EARMA	Information on RM ROADMAP and Action 17 communicated through EARMA Newsletter	Research communities	Newsletter
15	2023 Information on RM ROADMAP and Action 17, HETFA	Information on RM ROADMAP and Action 17 communicated through HETFA Newsletter	Research communities	Newsletter

From M12 onwards the consortium will prepare at least 3 publications relating to Researcher's time, Value proposition, Efficiency & effectiveness, Trust & accountability, Business case and more. For example HETFA aims to publish it in "Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education" <https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/tpsp20>, or to the SRAI Journal of Research Administration (based on the availability of funds for Open Access fees).

2.6 Events

During RM-ROADMAP, three main events / event series are envisaged, as described in Table 2 below.

Table 3. RM ROADMAP envisaged main events

Event type	Description	Timing
RM-Roadmap Workshop	Ambassadors, invited key stakeholders and cluster project representatives will meet once per year (3 in total) for an update on RM-ROADMAP progress, strategic discussions and to receive training on moderating the KCP and advocating for RM-ROADMAP at national/ regional level	Annual

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RM Helix event	Helix events are designed to generate discussion in the community of followers established on the Crowdhelix platform. A typical agenda features short briefs on exploitable results, pitches for new projects targeting open funding calls, and breakout discussions on emerging topics. The nature and objectives of each annual Helix event will be determined after the RM Helix is launched. Helix events may be virtual, or in person if co-located with another relevant Crowdhelix member event.	Annual Physical or Virtual
RM-Roadmap final event	Virtual conference to disseminate the results of RM-ROADMAP to stakeholders, including the project co-creation community, policy makers and partners engaging for further collaboration.	M34-M36

The events may be physical or virtual, or hybrid.

RM ROADMAP Ambassadors Meeting, May 9th, 2023

Figure 20. Group photo from the 1st Ambassadors Meeting in Prague, May 2023

Recruitment of (National) Ambassadors was completed by 31 May 2023 (milestone 3). As explained in D5.3 Coordination and Management report, the recruitment of the Communities of Practice Moderators will be completed by January 2024. The reason is that the subcategories of communities of practice need to be defined in WP1 also in close collaboration with the CARDEA Horizon Europe project "Career Acknowledgement for Research (Managers) Delivering for the European Area" and in alignment with the European Research Area (ERA) Action 17 on Research Management Initiative - Enhance the Strategic Capacity of Europe's Public Research Performing Organisations⁵.

115 ambassadors and associate ambassadors from 40 European countries have been recruited. The first RM Roadmap Ambassadors Meeting took place in Budapest, Hungary, May 9, 2023. The event commenced with a representative from HETFA, the local host, Renáta Anna Jaksa, Head of the Division for International Cooperation,

⁵ Overview of the ERA actions for the period 2022-2024 is available here: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/ec_rtd_era-policy-agenda-2021.pdf

addressing the attendees. The meeting highlighted the significance of research management in the research and innovation ecosystem in Europe. The event – that was hybrid - was attended by representatives from the consortium partners, the plethora of the RM ROADMAP Ambassadors and national and European policy makers. In addition to 20 partners and 60 RM Roadmap ambassadors joining in Budapest, 108 joined online. The broadcast/official launch is available on the EARMA YouTube channel [here](#) with 194 unique views by end of August 2023.

Several ambassadors delivered presentations in Budapest showcasing their experiences and ideas in relation to engaging with local communities during and after the RM Roadmap project.

Figure 21. Photos from the 1st Ambassadors Meeting in Prague, May 2023

A gender analysis conducted on of the ambassador’s network and found yielded the following breakdown: a) out of the 71 ambassadors, 43 are female, accounting for approximately 60.56% of the total ambassadors, b) out of the 44 associate ambassadors, 36 are female, making up approximately 81.82% of the total associate ambassadors. It should be noted that these numbers are based on a simplified gender analysis with the following limitations:

- (1) This is a desk exercise based on available data from the call for ambassadors done by the project team.
- (2) Ambassadors did not specify at application phase if they identified themselves with gender male or female. Furthermore, for the simplicity of this analysis, we have not included a third gender option which constitutes another limitation per se.

RM ROADMAP HELIX LAUNCH, Apr 24,2023

The Research Management Helix was launched at the 2023 EARMA Conference with great success. More information regarding the Helix is included in section 2.8.

Figure 22. Official RM ROADMAP Research Management Helix Launch at EARMA's 2023 Conference in Prague

It is important to note that RM ROADMAP was presented at the EARMA's yearly conference in Prague in 2023, the largest EARMA conference gathering yet, with over 1300 participants. The Conference's theme was Widening and Deepening of the RMA Profession.

Figure 23. The RM ROADMAP was presented at EARMA's 2023 Conference – RM ROADMAP in Depth. Partners have participated in international research management conferences, seminars and workshops and

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have endeavored to represent RM-ROADMAP to a plethora of audiences. Consortium representatives have networked and engaged with relevant stakeholders, as well as presented some of the core objectives of the project. Below is a list of these events with corresponding links to the relevant website:

Table 4. Workshop and conference organisation and/or participation of RM ROADMAP patterns promoting and/or presenting the objectives of RM ROADMAP

#	Lead Partner	Dissemination Type	Title	Start Date	Location	Link
1	EARMA	Organisation of a Workshop	Meeting with BESTPRAC thematic group	06-Sep-22	Belgrade, Serbia	https://earma.org/conferences/bestprac-thematic-group-meeting/
2	EARMA	Organisation of a Workshop	RM ROADMAP Kick Off Meeting	08-Sep-22	Belgrade Serbia	https://earma.org/media/documents/rm-roadmap-project-launch-morning-agenda-broadcast.pdf
3	HETFA	Organisation of a Workshop	'Research management, an emerging career opportunity within the research and innovation ecosystem' - Researchers' Night in Hungary	30-Sep-22	Budapest, Hungary	https://hetfa.eu/2022/10/workshop-on-research-management-at-researchers-night-organised-by-hetfa/
4	EARMA	Organisation of a Conference	EARMA Strategy Meeting	11-Oct-22	Sofia, Bulgaria	https://earma.org/news/sofia-earma-strategy-event/
5	HETFA	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	'V4 Training for Research Project Managers'	14-Oct-22	Brussels, Belgium	https://hetfa.eu/2022/10/hetfa-s-research-management-projects-showcased-at-the-v4-training-for-research-managers-in-brussels/
6	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	PURE International Conference 2022 - EARMA keynote	02-Nov-22	Porto, Portugal	https://www.elsevier.com/events/conferences/pure-international-conference-2022
7	EARMA	Participation to a Workshop	IGLO Implementation Working Group	10-Nov-22	Brussels, Belgium	
8	EARMA	Organisation of a Workshop	EARMA Leadership Event	22-Nov-22	Brussels, Belgium	https://earma.org/conferences/earma-leadership-event-2022/

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9	HETFA, NOVA, EARMA, CHX	Participation to a Workshop	foRMAtion final conference	30-Nov-22	Brussels, Belgium	https://www.formation-rma.eu/event/final-international-conference-of-the-formation-project/
10	EARMA	Participation to a Workshop	DARMA Leaders Meeting	07-Dec-22	Copenhagen, Denmark	https://darma.dk/darma-ledernetvaerksmode/
11	EARMA	Participation to a Workshop	Meeting with Horizon Europe Navigators - RMA's across Polish Academy of Sciences	12-Jan-23		https://polsca.pan.pl/en/events/horizon-europe-navigators-meetup-research-managers-administrators-rmas-2/
12	CHX	Organisation of a Workshop	CrowdHelix Members' event presentation: "Research Managers role in Open Innovation and international collaboration"	13-Jan-23	London, UK	https://crowdhelix.com/events/past?page=5
13	EARMA	Participation to a Workshop	Research Officers Network group Ireland	08-Feb-23	Ireland	
14	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	Marie Curie Alumni Association annual conference	24-Feb-23	Cordoba, Spain	https://earma.org/media/groups_resources/earma-members-general-assembly_secretaryearmaorg_earma-board-annual-report-to-the-general-assembly.pdf
15	EARMA	Participation to a Workshop	ERA Action 17, 1st ad hoc workshop	16-Mar-23	Brussels, Belgium	
16	EARMA	Participation to a Workshop	NARMA – RM ROADMAP – Lillestrom	21-Mar-23	Lillestrom, Norway	https://narma.no/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/RM-Roadmap-presentation-for-NARMA_20230320.pdf
17	EARMA, HETFA, NOVA, CHX	Participation to a Workshop	BESTPRAC Thematic group meeting	28,29-Mar-23	Larnaca, Cyprus	https://bestprac.eu/fileadmin/mediapool-bestprac/documents/EARMA-202303-Cyprus/BESTPRAC_Thematic_group_meeting_Cyprus_preliminary_programme080223.pdf
18	HETFA	Participation to a Conference	V4 conference for research managers	31-Mar-23	Brussels, Belgium	www.dzs.cz/sites/default/files/2023-04/V4Training%20PROGRAMME%20Spring%202023%20FINAL.pdf

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19	EARMA, HETFA, NOVA, CHX	Organisation of a Conference	EARMA Annual Conference	24-Apr-23	Prague, Czechia	https://earma.org/conferences/earma-conference-prague-2023/
20	EARMA, all partners	Organisation of a Workshop	1st RM ROADMAP Ambassadors Meeting	09-May-23	Budapest, Hungary	https://www.rmroadmap.eu/news-events/rm-roadmap-appoints-120-expert-research-managers-as-national-ambassadors
21	EARMA, all partners	Participation to a Workshop	ERA Action 17, 2nd ad hoc workshop	09-May-23	Budapest, Hungary	
22	EARMA, NOVA, CHX	Participation to a Conference	INORMS 2023	30,31-May-23	Durban, South Africa	https://az659834.vo.msecnd.net/eventsairwesteu/production-conference-public/160d11419ddd4e58a19ca720d4a76875
23	EARMA	Participation to a Conference	KOWI Annual conference	15-Jun-23	Rostock, Germany	https://www.kowi.de/en/kowi/services/training-events/annual-conference/kowi-annual-conference-on-eu-research-innovation-funding.aspx
24	EARMA	Participation to a Workshop	Professionalising Research Management in Catalonia	15-Jun-23	Barcelona, Spain	https://agaur.gencat.cat/en/details/activitatagenda/11-Trobada-de-gestors-2023
25	CHX	Organisation of a Training Webinar	Using the CrowdHelix Open Innovation Platform - Open webinar with a special focus on the Research Management Helix	25/07/2023	Online	https://crowdhelix.com/opportunities/using-the-crowdhelix-open-innovation-platform-open-webinar-with-a-special-focus-on-the-research-management-helix-2996

2.7 Videos

- The first video for RM ROADMAP was posted on the EARMA YouTube Channel and it was a recording of session from the Kick-off Meeting of the Project (8 September 2022). The broadcast/official launch is available on the EARMA YouTube channel [here](#) with 358 unique views by end of August 2023.

Figure 24. Screenshot from the RM ROADMAP Kick Off Meeting video - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Egb8WHhp_Fk

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AOQ2NEJOkpk&t=1s>

Search

1st RM Roadmap Ambassadors meeting

EARMA - Europea...

140 subscribers

Subscribe

Like

Share

163 views 1 month ago

The 1st RM Roadmap Ambassadors took place in Budapest, Hungary, May 9, 2023. [Show more](#)

Figure 25. Screenshot from the RM ROADMAP 1st Ambassadors Meeting Video - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HYRfKjdk768>

The second video was released in May 2023, and it was a recording from the 1st Ambassadors meeting hosted on EARMA's YouTube channel [here](#) with 194 unique views by end of August 2023.

The [third video](#), a professional video on the objectives of the projects and the Ambassadors was also released in May 2023, and served as an introduction to the RM ROADMAP project's first 120 Ambassadors. It is shared on RM ROADMAP's Research Management Helix on the Crowdfunder platform. The video has had over 130 views in the first month of its release.

Figure 26. Screenshot from the RM ROADMAP professional video for RM ROADMAP and the Ambassadors <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AOO2NEJOkpk&t=1s>

2.8 Clustering

Clusters, in the context of Horizon Europe, consist of related projects and initiatives with similar thematic focus and inter-dependent research activities that come together in common actions, events or meetings and share concepts, ideas and problems as well as communication and dissemination activities.

With respect to DCE, the primary project-project relationship to be established is with RM-ROADMAP's 'sister' project funded on the same call [HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-20], "CARDEA". Both consortia share a willingness to collaborate for the good of the RM community where synergies exist and have engaged early in the projects to develop a formal understanding.

RM ROADMAP has linked to Cardea's website on RM ROADMAP's home page with relevant links and information. Both projects will link to each other's tools and websites where relevant as soon as it is reasonably implementable. Both projects will initially include links and information on each other's projects on individual websites.

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

Towards a Europe-wide training and networking scheme for research managers

Further to RM Roadmap (Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area) the other EU project funded towards the Europe-wide scheme for research managers is [CARDEA - Career Acknowledgement for Research \(Managers\) Delivering for the European Area](#). Collaboration between the two projects will maximise impact.

Figure 27. Screenshot from RM ROADMAP with link to CARDEA's webpage

Eduard Balbuena Longo, University Professor at the Autonomous University of Barcelona and CARDEA representative also participated in the 1st RM ROADMAP Ambassadors meeting and discussed Career Acknowledgement for Research Managers Delivering for the European Area. This presentation looked at the preliminary findings of the CARDEA research and the socio-economic profile of a research manager that these results have discovered.

Figure 28. Professor Longo Eduard Balbuena Longo, CERCA and representative from the RM Roadmap sister project CARDEA discussed Career Acknowledgement for Research Managers Delivering for the European Area at the 1st Ambassadors meeting.

Other projects that have the potential to cluster on similar terms with RM-ROADMAP (and by extension, CARDEA), were listed in Appendix A of D4.1.

These include many projects funded under the broader call of HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01: “Reforming and Enhancing the European R&I System, part of the Horizon Europe’s “Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area” call (Destination 3).

2.9 Research Management Helix Launch

Figure 29. Material for promoting the Research Management Helix, at the launch of the Helix, at the EARMA 2023 conference in Prague

To drive impact, exploitation and dissemination activities, the RM ROADMAP consortium has developed a new virtual cluster/community titled the Research Management (RM) Helix on Crowdhelix’s custom-built AI-powered platform. The new Research Management Helix is calibrated to support RM ROADMAP through its various development stages, including post-project.

Crowdhelix is a pan-European Open Innovation Network that connects and enables research organisations, SMEs and industry to collaborate, innovate and grow. The Network has more than 650 member organisations from 57 countries and is present in all EU Member State countries.

The Network is set-up around thematic areas called “Helixes” and is supported by a technology platform (<https://www.crowdhelix.com/>), where these virtual communities are hosted. A Helix is a specialised community/cluster comprising experts and research and innovation professionals across research management, academia and industry. The Crowdhelix platform consists of multiple thematic helixes (currently 47), whose reach extends to 500,000+ research and innovation actors (across its members), and directly to more than 12000 users

currently on the Crowdhelix platform.

Figure 30. Some of the helixes on the Crowdhelix Open Innovation Platform ([https:// www.crowdhelix.com/helixes](https://www.crowdhelix.com/helixes))

The Crowdhelix platform facilitates connection between various types of stakeholders sharing common interests via the opportunities posted under up to three themed Helixes. It provides the following main functionalities:

- Announcements
- Collaboration opportunities posting
- Expertise offer
- Interaction with experts/organisations
- Results (at various levels of TRLs as well as best practices, policy papers and trainings).

Interested parties can contact the authors via public or private messages. The platform users can also engage proactively by using the search tool - which is refined by opportunities (posts), organisations, groups ("sub-organisations"), or experts (users) - to contact potential partners directly.

The Research Management (RM) Helix was officially successfully launched in month 8 of the RM ROADMAP project

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on the Crowdfelix platform at the biggest EARMA yearly international conference yet in Prague, April 2023 – see the corresponding digital leaflet in A.1 Annex 1.

research-management/info

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Background

Globalisation of research, complexity of funding and increasing transnational collaboration and mobility has been mirrored in the evolution of research management (RM). Virtually every research-active university and organisation now has a RM function, whether nascent or mature. Recognising that investing in research and innovation is, in essence, an investment in a sustainable future, many organisations are creating new modes of research office, who may provide support to individual researchers while representing strategic research programme objectives.

Variation in skillset, functions, capacity, and capabilities of RMs varies greatly, as does the national context in which they operate. However, key stakeholders including most funding bodies, now recognize that RM is developing into a truly global profession, with a growing necessity for skills, shared practices and professional networks. RM extends beyond universities, and its practitioners are found within funding bodies, charities, foundations, government, and industry.

Key Project: RM-ROADMAP

RM ROADMAP (Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area) will create a roadmap for the future of research management (RM) in Europe and a community to support the delivery of that roadmap. Coordinated by EARMA, RM-ROADMAP will connect existing European networks on a smart community platform which will enable an unprecedented co-creation process of RM in the world.

The RM-ROADMAP collaborators believe that investment in the RM community will facilitate and accelerate research results reaching the market and thereby the real economy. The project aims to (1) create and inform a bottom-up consensus on the future of RM in a roadmap, and (2) inform the community about the existing training, networking, funding, and mobility opportunities. This will support a pan-European network of RMs, supporting the establishment of strategic, cross-border partnerships between RMs in industry, Research Funding Organisations, higher education, and research institutions – never seen before at such a scale.

Research Management Helix

This Helix is an international Open Innovation community of RM practitioners, specialists, and other stakeholders, as well as relevant policy makers and citizen interest groups. In addition to facilitating opportunities that can further progress the RM domain of practice, the Helix will support RM-Roadmap by accelerating community development and translation of project results into cross-sectoral impact across the European Research Area and beyond.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101058475.

Funded by the European Union

Join us online for the 1st official RM Roadmap Ambassador's Meeting

1st RM Roadmap Ambassador Meeting

Past Event

Tue, May 9, 2023 09:00 AM - Tue, May 9, 2023 05:00 PM

[Learn more](#)

Seeking collaborators for Research Management projects?

Post a new Opportunity in this Helix

[New Post](#)

- 218 Experts
- 136 Organisations
- 51 Countries

RM ROADMAP Overview

Dr. Styliani Petroudi
Helix Manager

[Message](#)

"I'm delighted to have the opportunity to help enable the Research Management community to network, share their knowledge, and to drive improvements to the quality and impact of research projects through international collaboration."

Dr. David Langley
Helix Leader

Organisations

European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (EARMA)
Leading Organisation

Projects

RM ROADMAP
Key Project

Resources

Figure 31. Screenshot of the Research Management Helix on the Crowdfelix Open Innovation Platform, June 21, 2023.

The Crowdfelix platform has an existing pool of 12000 users, who are automatically notified upon the creation of a Helix. This means that the Crowdfelix users have access to all the posts, including the Research Management posts. Some opportunities also address cross-cutting topics, which may include up to three helixes. The Research Management Helix acts as a resource tool with links to the project website, social media and any Dissemination and Communication activities produced during the project.

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To facilitate joining the Research Management Helix on the CrowdHelix Platform CrowdHelix has created a dedicated account for the RM ROADMAP Project and the extended network that has been disseminated to the RM ROADMAP Ambassadors to promote to their networks.

Some opportunities already posted on the RM Helix on the CrowdHelix platform as presented below.

Figure 32. Screenshot of Opportunities on the Research Management Helix on the CrowdHelix Open Innovation Platform

The Helix contains information about the project, a list of the project members, and a resources tool with links to the project website and social media sites, and dissemination and communication materials (i.e. presentations, scientific publications, videos) produced during the project (by partner request). Partners will be requested to select and send these materials to the helix manager and ask him/her to promote them. The stakeholders will be notified by the platform about the advancements of RM ROADMAP project, with the aim of maximising the visibility of the results to actors best placed to make use of them.

The screenshot shows a post by Andreea Petrea for Crowdfunder, in the 'Announcements, Research Management' category. The title is 'Using the Crowdfunder Open Innovation Platform - Open webinar with a special focus on the Research Management Helix'. The post is associated with 'RM ROADMAP'. It lists 'Event Attendee' as the role sought, and 'Collaboration', 'Open innovation', and 'Research management' as areas of expertise. The text describes an open webinar on July 25th from 11 am CEST, introducing the Crowdfunder platform and its matchmaking capabilities. A 'Funded by the European Union' badge is visible at the bottom.

Figure 33. Announcement of an online event to promote the use of the Research Management Helix on the Crowdfunder Open Innovation Platform

The consortium, the RM Helix and the Knowledge Community Platform aim to leverage existing connections and create new ones to disseminate to raise awareness and engagement for the future of the RM profession.

The RM Helix was expected to attract 150 stakeholders to join the Helix – engaging with the RM ROADMAP project - by M36. The launch of the Helix was communicated to the users of the platform in a dedicated post. Due to the wide dissemination and engagement of RM ROADMAP **the RM Helix already boasts over 300 users and 170 organisations and 53 countries by the end of M12** (the slight difference in numbers in different figures included in the report have to do with the specific time that the screenshots were taken as the numbers have continued to increase).

Figure 34. Percentage of RM Helix membership from Widening Countries vs other European Countries.

The figure above presents the proportion of members of the Research Management Helix, from widening and other European and other countries at the middle of August 2023. This percentage highlighting the memberships from Widening Countries was at this time just under 33%. The distribution of the Research Management Helix Members at the same time can be seen at the figure below. Please note that the numbers change as more members join the Research Management Helix.

Figure 35. The distribution of RM Helix members across the Widening Countries.

Opportunities and results will continue to be shared through the Helix Platform that will result in wide dissemination of the projects activities and results and empower the RM community across Europe and beyond. RM ROADMAP is actively engaging and supporting the RM ROADMAP Ambassadors to enhance dissemination and communication of results.

2.10 Key Exploitable Results

Two Key Exploitable Results (KERs) are envisaged from RM-ROADMAP. During DCE initiation, KERs are described, located within the project workplan, and an initial assessment of their impact pathway performed:

- Roadmap: a summary of all findings of the RM ROADMAP activities, to provide input for EU and national policy making, with specific attention to the European Research Area and Widening participation. The primary European roadmap will also include national, regional and/or thematic annexes.
- the KCP Platform: the Knowledge and Community Platform of RM ROADMAP is constituted from two different systems and is described in great detail in Deliverable D4.2 Online Knowledge and Community Platform, one for cocreation and another for dissemination and impact acceleration. As explained in D4.2 one system will be developed for cocreation and another for system will be a helix on the Crowdhelix platform – the Research Management Helix.

In later phases, through the tasks of WP6, detailed plans for sustained exploitation of the KERs will be explored, and strategic action plans put in place to maximise the likelihood of exploitation and potential value realised from the results.

3. Milestones and Performance Monitoring

RM ROADMAP’s Communication Plan presents the different activities with the purpose of informing about the project but also its main results and impacts. In the first 12 months of the RM ROADMAP project, the communication and dissemination activities have been timely, accurate and coordinated to address the right audiences. The different actions were correctly tailored to target the different audience segments to inform about the project and bring the community together. This can be demonstrated by the numbers reached in the first year of the RM ROADMAP.

The table below Table 5.: Performance measures, linked objectives and targets for Dissemination Communication and Exploitation lists the performance measures, linked objectives and targets for Dissemination Communication and Exploitation as presented in Deliverable D4.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Plan and the RM ROADMAP Grant Agreement. These Performance measures are aligned with the Communication Key Performance Indicators included Communication Plan of the project.

Table 5.: Performance measures, linked objectives and targets for Dissemination Communication and Exploitation

ACTIVITIES	Objective	Milestone / Schedule	Key Performance Indicator(s)	Target (end of project unless otherwise stated)	Number reached at M12 of the RM ROADMAP project
Research Management Helix	Establish an active community of cross-discipline and cross-sector stakeholders, suitable for project dissemination and impact acceleration activities	Scoping from M1; established in line with KCP; maintained at least 5 years beyond the project or as long as valuable	Number of organisations represented in followers	150	300 Experts (66 out of widening countries, 144 from other European Countries) 165 Organisations 54 Countries
Project website	Display project key facts to a general audience. Direct specific audiences to other channels (e.g. KCP, social media, mailing list, direct contact)	M1 onwards and 5 years beyond the term [Project Milestone 1]	Number of visits	2000	16000 Unique visits
Social media	Three channels actively posting relevant content	Establish at project KO	Number of followers	300 followers across Twitter, LinkedIn, ResearchGate	2 channels over 600 followers across LinkedIn and Twitter
			Impressions (general public reach)	20 000	28000 impressions
Partners’ websites	Each partner to be conveying project information to their own audience	As defined by partners task involvement	Number of pages	1 dedicated webpage area per partner website	1 dedicated webpage area per partner website
Newsletters	Share projects activities, disseminate results and encourage engagement from interested audiences via mailing list (self-	One per year starting M12	Open rate per newsletter to mailing list	25% open rate per newsletter	NA yet. Information on RM ROADMAP has been included in newsletters by EARMA (reach 5000) and HETFA (reach 1400)
			Number of views on social media.	(no target)	

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	signup) and social media				
Media Engagement	Share project activities, multiply communications and calls to action, acknowledge funding sources	Continuous before, during and after project	Number of press releases / popular articles	6	3
			Number of media appearances per partner	6	1
Project workshops	Share project activities & engage with stakeholders	Annual	Number of overall participants	>80 per workshop	80 with physical presence over 100 with online presence
			Events attended by policy representatives	4	2
Project final conference	Virtual event to share project results &, engage with stakeholders	M34	Number of participants	>200	NA
Other international events	Showcase RM-ROADMAP, share progress and disseminate results to target audiences (i.e academic conferences, professional association fairs and events)	As per target event schedule (Appendix B)	Number of participations / appearances	10 (NB this amalgamates general int'l and professional event targets in GA Part II)	7 (BESTPRAC, EARMA, INORMS, CHX RTO, Marie Curie Alumni, Formation Event, V4 Event, etc) (These events are presented in Table 4. Workshop and conference organisation and/or participation of RM ROADMAP patterns promoting and/or presenting the objectives of RM ROADMAP).
Other regional events	Showcase RM-ROADMAP, share progress and disseminate results with a focus on the regional dimension of the project		Number of participations / appearances per partner	6	5 (NARMA, DARMA, Kowi, Polish Academy of Sciences, Research Officers Ireland, etc) (These events are presented in Table 4. Workshop and conference organisation and/or participation of RM ROADMAP patterns promoting and/or presenting the objectives of RM ROADMAP).
Publications	Disseminate project results to relevant target groups through scientific, professional and/or popular publications	As results are available; continues beyond project term	Number of articles	3-4	NA

4. Conclusions

The RM ROADMAP Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Report (D4.4) summarizes the

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Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Activities of RM ROADMAP in the first 12 months of the project. The report presents a summary of the different activities that have by far exceeded the expected according to the timeline of the project.

The website of RM ROADMAP has had over 16000 unique visits in the first 12 months of the project and the social media of RM ROADMAP (i.e. its Twitter and LinkedIn account) have more than 28000 impressions and more than 1300 engagements since January 2023.

The Research Management Helix was launched in a dedicated session at the EARMA 2023 conference in April, and now the Helix has over 300 members, from over 160 organization and 54 countries. These numbers are higher than the expected engagement by Month 36 of the project.

The first Ambassadors meeting took place in May 2023 with over 80 participants with physical presence and over 100 participants online. RM ROADMAP has 115 ambassadors from 40 countries that will lead the onboarding of the RM Community to the Knowledge and Communication Platform.

The Consortium has successfully promoted RM ROADMAP on many other channels including the Research Professional News, EARMA, EUA, and HETFA websites well as through the Crowdhelix platform, the networks BESTPRAC, ASTP, KOWI etc. and through national networks in dedicated events such as those of DARMA, NARMA, etc. This was partly achieved through the participation and/or organisation of different events such as international and national conferences and workshops e.g., EARMA 2023, INORMS 2023, etc. The relevant information can be found in Table 4. Workshop and conference organisation and/or participation of RM ROADMAP patterns promoting and/or presenting the objectives of RM ROADMAP. Other communication activities are presented in Table 2. List of Communication Activities related to RM ROADMAP.

Furthermore, RM ROADMAP has successfully contacted other clusters and projects such as CARDEA and Formation. Successful contact with other clusters and projects such as CARDEA, Formation etc.

It is important to note that the RM ROADMAP consortium engaged actively in the dissemination of the project. The Key Performance Indicators reported in this deliverable are consistent if not higher to the expected numbers. This demonstrates the dedication of the RM ROADMAP Consortium to the project's objectives and ERA Action 17, i.e. to identify and adapt the research management capital base of the European Union (EU), including the widening countries, and emerging needs of its current and future research management workforce to improve the EU's competitiveness and sustain its economic performance.

Annexes

A1 Annex 1 Joining the RM Helix Dissemination Leaflet

The RM Helix Leaflet disseminated at EARMA Conference 2023, where the helix was launched.

Connecting and Commercialising the World of Research

- COLLABORATE**
Connect with 12,000 innovators, researchers and business leaders.
- ACCELERATE**
Fast track consortium building using our unique AI powered recommender engine.
- COMMERCIALISE**
Leverage our Helix communities to engage with stakeholders, investors and policymakers.

Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram icons

RESEARCH MANAGEMENT HELIX

www.rmroadmap.eu

What is the Research Management Helix?

The Research Management Helix is an online community where research managers can share ideas, knowledge and best practice.

Who is it for?

Anybody involved in research management activities. We recognise that research managers have a broad range of specialisms and we want to create a space where they can share knowledge and experiences.

Why join?

The Research Management Helix will harness CrowdHelix's unique AI-powered recommender engine to establish an online community that will shape the future of our profession. The Helix will also give you access to valuable learning resources and professional development opportunities that can help you advance your career.

How do I join?

Visit the Research Management Helix on the CrowdHelix website www.crowdhelix.com. You can also speak with members of the CrowdHelix team at the EARMA conference.

Scan here to join the Research Management Helix, learn more about the platform and connect with our team

hello@crowdhelix.com
www.crowdhelix.com

A.2 Annex 2 RM ROADMAP Sessions at EARMA 2023

A summary of the 4 Sessions for RM ROADMAP at the EARMA International Conference in Prague in 2023.

The screenshots show the following content:

- Top Left Screenshot:** EARMA Conference Prague 2023 banner with navigation links: Partners, Terms and Conditions, Programme Legend, Conference Prices, Programme.
- Top Right Screenshot:** Session programme details for 'RM ROADMAP in Depth' on Wednesday 26 April 2-4:45 p.m. (Europe/Prague). It includes a description of the project, a list of 4 sessions (Co-Creation Exercise, Research Management Helix, Action 17 and pilot projects, RM Roadmap in Depth), and a link to the website.
- Bottom Left Screenshot:** 'Presenters' section listing: Nik Claesen, Viliq Zsár, Carolina Varela, and Borana Taraj.
- Bottom Right Screenshot:** EARMA Conference Prague 2023 banner with navigation links: Partners, Terms and Conditions, Programme Legend, Conference Prices, Programme.

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

programme **Roadmap)**

By CrowdHelix and EARMA
 Category: Presentation | Topic: Professional Development and Recognition

Tuesday 25 April 2:15 p.m. - 2:45 p.m. (Europe/Prague) (Expired)

North Hall

In this presentation CrowdHelix will explain and demonstrate their new Research Management Helix. This Helix is being launched during the conference as an integral part of the RM Roadmap project and designed for use by the research management community. It will act as the main dissemination channel for RM Roadmap but also feature other research management posts, opportunities and training possibilities

Presentations and Q&A by:

- David Langley (CrowdHelix, Chief of Strategy)
- Caia Jurgens (CrowdHelix, Network Development Lead,)
- Nikl Claesen (EARMA Managing Director)

The RM Roadmap project is a Horizon Europe funded CSA project. It is a pilot project underpinning ERA Action 17 (Research Management Initiative). The goal of the project and Action 17 are to give direction to research management in Europe. Please find more information here:
<https://www.rmroadmap.eu/>

Please find the 4 sessions related to RM Roadmap at the conference here:

1. Co-Creation Exercise
2. Research Management Helix

programme **3. Action 17 and pilot projects**
4. RM Roadmap in Depth

Presenters

- David Langley
- Mr Caia Jurgens
- Nikl Claesen

EARMA
 European Association of Research Managers and Administrators

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programme **EARMMA**

EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF RESEARCH MANAGERS AND ADMINISTRATORS

Menu LOGIN

EARMA Conference Prague April 24-26, 2023

EARMA Conference Prague 2023

- Partners
- Terms and Conditions
- Programme Legend
- Conference Prices
- Programme

Conference RM ROADMAP Co-Creation And Help

programme **Ambassadors**

Category: Presentation | Topic: Professional Development and Recognition

Tuesday 25 April 1:45 p.m. - 2:15 p.m. (Europe/Prague) (Expired)

North Hall

This session will give an overview of the Co-Creation exercise in the Research Management Roadmap Project (RM Roadmap). This co-creation will be made possible through a network of over 100 ambassadors across over 40 countries in Europe.

The RM Roadmap project is a Horizon Europe funded CSA project. It is a pilot project underpinning ERA Action 17 (Research Management Initiative). The goal of the project and Action 17 are to give direction to research management in Europe. Please find more information here:
<https://www.rmroadmap.eu/>

Please find the 4 sessions related to RM Roadmap at the conference here:

1. Co-Creation Exercise
2. Research Management Helix
3. Action 17 and pilot projects
4. RM Roadmap in Depth

Presenters

- Nikl Claesen
- Olaf Svenningsen

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

<p>13:20, 6:28 PM</p> <p>RM ROADMAP Co-Creation and Anticipation session</p> <p>Dr Evelina Brännvall</p> <p>Borana Taraj</p> <p>CONTACT US</p> <p>TERMS & CONDITIONS</p> <p>PRIVACY STATEMENT</p> <p>GDPR</p> <p>©2020-2023 EARMA</p> <p>https://www.earma.eu/en/2023/04/earma-conference-prague-2023/</p> <p>33</p>	<p>13:20, 6:28 PM</p> <p>Research Management Momentum in the ERA session</p> <p>EARMA EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF RESEARCH MANAGERS AND ADMINISTRATORS</p> <p>LOGIN</p> <p>Menu</p> <p>EARMA EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF RESEARCH MANAGERS AND ADMINISTRATORS</p> <p>EARMA Conference Prague April 24-26, 2023</p> <p>EARMA Conference Prague 2023</p> <p>EARMA Conference Prague 2023</p> <p>Partners</p> <p>Terms and Conditions</p> <p>Programme Legend</p> <p>Conference Prices</p> <p>Programme</p> <p>Conference</p> <p>2 Research Management Momentum</p> <p>Help</p> <p>https://www.earma.eu/en/2023/04/earma-conference-prague-2023/</p> <p>34</p>
<p>13:20, 6:28 PM</p> <p>programme</p> <p>In The ERA</p> <p>Action 17, RM Roadmap and Cardea</p> <p>Category: Oral 60 Mins Topic: None</p> <p>Tuesday 25 April 3 p.m. - 4 p.m. (Europe/Prague) (Expired)</p> <p>Panorama Hall</p> <p>Research Management Momentum in the ERA: Action 17, RM Roadmap and CARDEA</p> <p>There is a very strong research management momentum in Europe. This session will give an overview of the EU policy developed in action 17 by the EC and the stakeholders of the action. The action will be underpinned by two projects of which one is coordinated by EARMA. These projects are RM ROADMAP (https://www.rmroadmap.eu/) and CARDEA (https://www.ucc.ie/en/hr/research/university-humanresources-research/).</p> <p>You will get an insight into the policy and how both projects mean to contribute and create impact on research management.</p> <p>This session will be moderated by Borana Taraj.</p> <p>Speakers:</p> <p>Action 17: Stijn Delaure (EC, DG R&I, Unit A3, R&I Actors and Research Careers)</p> <p>RM Roadmap: Nik Claesen (EARMA, Managing Director)</p> <p>CARDEA: Prof. Eduard Balbuena (Professor Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona and ICERCA)</p> <p>The RM Roadmap project is a Horizon Europe funded CSA project. It is a pilot project underpinning ERA Action 17 (Research</p> <p>https://www.earma.eu/en/2023/04/earma-conference-prague-2023/</p> <p>35</p>	<p>13:20, 6:28 PM</p> <p>Research Management Momentum in the ERA session</p> <p>Management initiative). The goal of the project and Action 17 are to give direction to research management in Europe. Please find more information here: https://www.rmroadmap.eu/</p> <p>Please find the 4 sessions related to RM Roadmap at the conference here:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Co-Creation Exercise 2. Research Management Helix 3. Action 17 and pilot projects 4. RM Roadmap in Depth <p>Presenters</p> <p>Nik Claesen</p> <p>Stijn Delaure</p> <p>Prof Dr Eduard Balbuena</p> <p>Moderators</p> <p>Borana Taraj</p> <p>https://www.earma.eu/en/2023/04/earma-conference-prague-2023/</p> <p>36</p>

A.3 Annex 3 RM ROADMAP M7-M12 Website Analytics

RM Roadmap Website Analytics

Traffic

February 24th - August 25th

VISITS	BOUNCE RATE	UNIQUE VISITORS	PAGEVIEWS
23K	91.87%	22K	16K
+100% yr/yr	+100% yr/yr	+100% yr/yr	+100% yr/yr

Visits

Feb 24, 2022–Aug 25, 2023 • 22,963 Total +100% yr/yr

Monthly

Figure 1 - All website visitors from February 24th - August 25th

Top Devices by Visits

Top Sources by Visits VIEW SOURCES

Figure 2 - All website visits across devices and sources from February 24th - August 25th

Top Operating Systems by Visits

Top Browsers by Visits

Figure 3 - All website visits across different operating systems and browsers from February 24th - August 25th

Geography

February 24th - August 25th

Figure 4 - All website visits by country from February 24th - August 25th

Location	Visits
▶ Portugal	1,884 (8.20%)
▶ Spain	1,588 (6.91%)
▶ Netherlands	1,428 (6.22%)
▶ Belgium	1,414 (6.16%)
▶ France	1,408 (6.13%)
▶ Italy	1,186 (5.16%)
▶ Czechia	1,147 (4.99%)
▶ Ireland	1,070 (4.66%)
▶ Hungary	1,023 (4.45%)
▶ United Kingdom	898 (3.91%)

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▶ Norway	818 (3.56%)
▶ Germany	796 (3.47%)
▶ Finland	732 (3.19%)
▶ Croatia	623 (2.71%)
▶ Austria	603 (2.63%)
▶ United States	540 (2.35%)
▶ Turkey	477 (2.08%)
▶ Switzerland	405 (1.76%)
▶ Sweden	386 (1.68%)
▶ Cyprus	371 (1.62%)

Figure 5 - List of all website visits by country from February 24th - August 25th

Traffic Sources

February 24th - August 25th

Figure 6 - Source of all website visits from February 24th - August 25th

Source	Visits
Direct	19,083 (83.1%)
Search	1,913 (8.33%)
Social	1,193 (5.20%)
Referral	657 (2.86%)
Email	117 (0.51%)

Source	Visits
Search	1,913 (8.33%)
Google	1,783
Bing	107
Ecosia	11
DuckDuckGo	9
Yahoo!	2
Yandex	1

Figure 7 - Number of website visitors by source from February 24th - August 25th

RM Roadmap_ CHX_WP4_D4.4_Preliminary Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Report

▼ Social	1,193 (5.20%)
▶ LinkedIn	785
▶ Twitter	329
Facebook	79

Figure 8 - Number of website visitors by social platform from February 24th - August 25th

▼ Referral	657 (2.86%)
▶ surveymonkey.com	199
▶ hetfa.eu	102
▶ statics.teams.cdn.office.net	76
▶ researchprofessionalnews.c...	28
▶ czarma.cz	27
▶ wbc-rti.info	25
▶ wiki.eduuni.fi	24
▶ euresearch.ch	15
▶ vedavyzkum.cz	15
▶ hetfa.hu	14
▶ astp4kt.eu	10
▶ era.avcr.cz	9
▶ italianresearchmanagers.eu	9
▶ cyl.ac.cy	9
▶ email.seznam.cz	8
▶ portal.bionanotech.ro	7
▶ researchprofessional.com	7

Figure 9 - Number of website visitors by referral website from February 24th - August 25th

Site Content

February 24th - August 25th

Figure 10 - Most popular pages of the website from February 24th - August 25th

All Pages with Views
Feb 24, 2022–Aug 25, 2023 • 15,798 Total +0% yr/yr

Page	Views	Time on Page	Bounce Rate	Exit Rate
Home ↗ /	8,617	00:02:12	91.46%	86.65%
Ambassador Programme ↗ /faq	6,108	00:03:31	92.74%	86.76%
RM Roadmap Appoints 120 Expert Research Managers as National Ambassa /news-events/rm-roadmap-appoints-120-expert-research-managers-as-national-ambassa	394	00:05:02	94.2%	81.98%
News & Events ↗ /news-events	348	00:00:28	84.73%	55.75%
Community Connect ↗ /community-connect	84	00:00:33	91.84%	63.1%
Project Workflow ↗ /project-workflow	74	00:02:27	91.84%	67.57%
Project Team_230528 ↗ /project-team_230528	65	00:03:15	88.1%	70.77%
RM Roadmap Cardea ↗ /sisterprojects	65	00:04:44	95.45%	80%
Project-Team ↗ /new-page-1	21	00:01:08	81.25%	80.95%

Figure 11 - Most popular pages and further detail of the website from February 24th - August 25th

A.4 Annex 4 RM ROADMAP Social Media Analytics

RM ROADMAP Social Media Analytics

Twitter

The Twitter account for RM Roadmap has **285 followers** and has posted **123 tweets** (as of August 17th, 2023). The following tables and figures will explore Twitter Analytics and include impressions, engagement and more.

<u>Period</u>	<u>Total Impressions</u>	<u>Engagement Rate</u>
January 1st to August 17th	10,800 (44 Daily Average)	3.9%

Table 1 - Impressions and Engagement Rate of the LinkedIn page from January 1st to August 15th

January 1st to April 1st

<u>Period</u>	<u>Total Impressions</u>	<u>Engagement Rate</u>
January 1st to April 1st	5,000 (55 daily average)	1.8%

Table 2 - Impressions and Engagement Rate of the Twitter page from January 1st to April 1st

Your Tweets earned **5.0K impressions** over this **91 day** period

Figure 1 - Tweet Impressions from January 1st to April 1st

Figure 2 - Engagement rate, link clicks, likes and retweets from January 1st to April 1st

April 2nd to June 30th

<u>Period</u>	<u>Total Impressions</u>	<u>Engagement Rate</u>
April 2nd to June 30th	4,500 (50 Daily Average)	4.7%

Table 3 - Impressions and Engagement Rate of the Twitter page from April 2nd to June 30th

Your Tweets earned **4.5K impressions** over this **90 day** period

Figure 3 - Tweet Impressions from April 2nd to June 30th

Your Tweets earned **4.5K impressions** over this **90 day** period

Figure 4 - Tweet Impressions from April 2nd to June 30th

Figure 5 - Engagement rate, link clicks, likes and retweets from April 2nd to June 30th

Tweets	Top Tweets	Tweets and replies	Promoted	Impressions	Engagements	Engagement rate
	<p>RM ROADMAP Project @RMROADMAP · Jun 21</p> <p>Last week, Cristina Oliveira from @NOVAuni represented #RMRoadmap at the 11th Research Managers meeting under the title "Professionalising Research Management" in Barcelona, Spain.</p> <p>The event focused on best practices and the professionalism of research managers 🍷 pic.twitter.com/riaNcYbpnc</p> <p>View Tweet activity</p>			493	61	12.4%
	<p>RM ROADMAP Project @RMROADMAP · May 25</p> <p>The 120 national ambassadors of @RMROADMAP will work together to strengthen Europe's capacity in research and innovation.</p> <p>They will achieve this by fostering a bottom-up consensus to shape the future of the research management profession.</p> <p>Read more 📄 bit.ly/3MBWMA0</p> <p>View Tweet activity</p>			285	60	21.1%

Figure 6 - Top tweets from April 2nd to June 30th

July 1st to August 17th

<u>Period</u>	<u>Total Impressions</u>	<u>Engagement Rate</u>
July 1st to August 17th	1,300 (27 Daily Average)	5.2%

Table 4 - Impressions and Engagement Rate of the Twitter page from July 1st to August 17th

Your Tweets earned **1.3K impressions** over this **48 day** period

Figure 7 - Tweet Impressions from July 1st to August 17th

Figure 8 - Engagement rate, link clicks, likes and retweets from July 1st to August 17th

	RM ROADMAP Project @RMRoadmap · Jul 6 The #RMRoadmap Project seeks to create framework conditions for #ResearchManagement to strengthen the European Research Area Learn more about the objectives of #RMRoadmap bit.ly/43bXz1G View Tweet activity	418	25	6.0%
	RM ROADMAP Project @RMRoadmap · Jul 14 Pioneering researchers and innovators are working together on #RMRoadmap They hope to drive efficiency and effectiveness in the delivery of complex research programmes, pursue quality in research and innovation and more! Discover our partners bit.ly/43bXz1G View Tweet activity	230	25	10.9%
	RM ROADMAP Project @RMRoadmap · Aug 9 Discover the ultimate self-development tool The foRMation training program offers lifelong learning for students and RMAs. This unique opportunity can enhance their skills and advance their careers. Join the helix and learn more bit.ly/3OKtoud View Tweet activity	81	10	12.3%
	RM ROADMAP Project @RMRoadmap · Aug 16 Meet the Team: The Cyprus Institute @CyprusInstitute serves as an EU gateway to research and technology in the Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East region, promoting cooperation among the peoples of the region for a better future Learn more bit.ly/43bXz1G View Tweet activity	54	0	0.0%

Figure 9 - Top tweets from July 1st to August 17th

LinkedIn

The LinkedIn account for RM Roadmap currently (as of August 15th, 2023) has **546 followers**. The following tables and figures will look at follower demographics and content growth.

<u>Period</u>	<u>Total Impressions</u>	<u>Engagement Rate</u>
January 1st to August 15th	17,252	5.13%
		762 Reactions
		13 Comments
		110 Reposts

Table 5 - Impressions and Engagement Rate of the LinkedIn page from January 1st to August 15th

Metrics

Figure 10 - Post Impressions from January 1st to August 15th

January 1st to March 28th

<u>Period</u>	<u>Total Impressions</u>	<u>Engagement Rate</u>
January 1st to March 28th	1,643	5,17%
		69 Reactions
		0 Comments
		16 Reposts

Table 6 - Impressions and Engagement Rate of the LinkedIn page from January 1st to March 28th

Metrics

Impressions ▾

Figure 11 - Post Impressions from January 1st to March 28th

March 29th to June 26th

<u>Period</u>	<u>Total Impressions</u>	<u>Engagement Rate</u>
March 29th to June 26th	11,736	5,54%
		563 Reactions
		12 Comments
		75 Reposts

Table 7 - Impressions and Engagement Rate of the LinkedIn page from March 29th to June 26th

Figure 12 - Post Impressions from March 29th to June 26th

June 27th to August 15th

<u>Period</u>	<u>Total Impressions</u>	<u>Engagement Rate</u>
June 27th to August 15th	3,876	3.87%
		130 Reactions
		1 Comments
		19 Reposts

Table 8 - Impressions and Engagement Rate of the LinkedIn page from June 27th to August 15th

Metrics

Figure 13 - Post Impressions from June 27th to August 15th

Followers

Follower metrics ?

Figure 14 - Total follower growth from January 1st to August 15th

Follower demographics

Figure 15 - Follower demographics from January 1st to August 15th

January to March

Figure 16 - Total follower growth from January 1st to March 28th

March to June

Figure 17 - Total follower growth from March 29th to June 26th

June to August

Follower highlights

547
Total followers

75
New followers in the last 50 days
▼ 60.9%

Follower metrics

Figure 18 - Total follower growth from June 27th to August 15th

Visitors to LinkedIn Page

Visitor highlights ?

1,827
Page views

805
Unique visitors

66
Custom button clicks

Visitor metrics ?

Page views ▾ All pages ▾ All filters

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Desktop	830
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Mobile	997

Figure 19 - Visitors to the LinkedIn page from January 1st to August 15th

Visitor demographics ?

Figure 20 - Visitor demographics from January 1st to August 15th

Overall LinkedIn and Twitter Statistics

<u>Period</u>	<u>Total Impressions</u>	<u>Engagement Rate</u>
January 1st to August 1th	10,800 (44 Daily Average)	3.9%

Table 9 - Twitter social media statistics

<u>Period</u>	<u>Total Impressions</u>	<u>Engagement Rate</u>
January 1st to August 15th	17,252	5.13% 762 Reactions 13 Comments 110 Reposts

Table 10 - LinkedIn social media statistics

<u>Period</u>	<u>Total Impressions</u>	<u>Engagement Rate</u>
January 1st to August 17th	28,052	4.66% 1,306 Engagements

Table 11 - Overall social media statistics

RM ROADMAP

 rmroadmap.eu

 [@rmroadmap](https://twitter.com/rmroadmap)

 [linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap](https://www.linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap)

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.